

Extractive Separation of Molybdenum by Complexation with Thiocyanate and Selective Stripping of the Interfering Elements using Dithionite^ψ

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Solvent extraction separation of molybdenum with thiocyanate is mostly confined to the extractive photometric determination of the metal ion in microgram amounts¹, and where milligram quantities are employed, the methods² have been used for the removal of molybdenum(VI) from rhenium(VII) but not for the quantitative separation of the metal ion itself. The various factors affecting this separation are discussed here and a procedure is given.

Results and Discussion

Upto 6 mg Mo in 10 ml aqueous phase, the maximum extraction obtained was 99.6% from 0.75–2.5 M HCl solution containing 1–7 ml (40-fold excess) of 20% KSCN, but at higher concentrations the extraction was incomplete. Three contacts with the solvent (10 + 5 + 5 ml) left less than 0.00027% Mo in the aqueous phase. An additional 0.4 ml of 20% KSCN was added to the aqueous phase, each time, before the second and subsequent extractions were made as it was also extracted (~90%) by the solvent. Equilibrium between the solvent and the aqueous phase was attained in 2.5–5 min. It was found that higher than 1.5 ml KSCN (20%) increased the coextraction of interfering elements to a considerable extent. Therefore, the optimal range of molybdenum extraction corresponding to 1.5 ml concentration of KSCN in technical samples was found to be 0.005–6 mg. Ethyl acetate was found to be the best solvent giving maximum (99.6%) extraction of Mo. Dithionite used as solid in the wash solution acted as a reducing agent for Mo^{VI}, Fe^{III} and Se^{IV} and made the last two elements easily back-washable in their reduced states. The aqueous solution of dithionite was unstable to acids. So it was added as solid (200–500 mg) after the addition of wash solution and the contents were shaken immediately. Hg, Pd and Sb were either reduced or formed coloured precipitates with dithionite and were selectively back-extracted. Preferential back-washing of the interfering elements (leaving Mo^V-SCN complex quantitatively in the organic extract) was achieved only when the wash solution contained HCl and KSCN besides dithionite in the desired concentration. Molybdenum was back-extracted completely from the solvent by two contacts of alkaline water (10 + 10 ml) containing a small excess of H₂O₂ to dissolve the pre-

cipitated molybdenum(V) hydroxide. The thiocyanate in the back-extract being a mild reducing agent, interfered in the titration of Mo^V with Ce^{IV} solution and was destroyed³ by boiling the alkaline solution with H₂O₂ only for 4–5 min, whereas the acid destruction method took hours.

Effect of diverse ions : Sulphate, nitrate, chloride, bromide and iodide, 200 mg each; thiourea, borate, EDTA, citrate, fluoride and ascorbic acid, 100 mg each; sulphite, bicarbonate, carbonate, tartrate and phosphate, 50 mg each; acetate, 20 mg; glycerol, 0.5 ml; and H₂O₂ (20 volume), 2 ml did not affect the extraction of 5 mg molybdenum when present in 10 ml aqueous phase. Oxalate (5 mg) lowered the extraction by more than 3%. Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Si^{IV}, Cd^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Pb^{II}, and U^{VI}, 10 mg each; V^V, Au^{III}, Ta^V, Re^{VII}, Th^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, Ag^I, Zr^{IV} and Al^{III}, 1 mg each; Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV}, 0.5 mg each were not extracted. The extractions of Ti^{IV}, 10 mg (50%); Nb^V, 1 mg (50%); W^{VI}, 0.3 mg (50%); Cu^{II}, 5 mg (40%); and Cr^{VI}, 10 mg (10%) were decreased to nil in the presence of 100 mg each of sodium fluoride, thiourea and ascorbic acid respectively, whereas Fe^{III}, 10 mg (90%); Pd^{II}, 0.5 mg (80%); Hg^{II}, 5 mg (70%); Se^{IV}, 1 mg (50%) and Sb^{III}, 10 mg (30%) were completely removed from the organic phase by shaking with the wash solution after adding dithionite. Iron(II,III) had a tendency to develop pink colour in the organic extract. A second back-wash as recommended in the procedure would suffice to overcome this difficulty. Only Sn^{II}, 10 mg (80%); Co^{II}, 10 mg (70%); Os^{VIII}, 0.5 mg (50%); and Ru^{III}, 0.5 mg (10%) accompany molybdenum (extraction in parenthesis).

Applications : The different combinations of synthetic samples (containing mg amounts of metal ions) were : (i) Fe(10), (Mo added 10, found 9.91); (ii) V(1) + Ni(5) + Mn(5) (Mo added 5, found 4.86); (iii) Cu(5) + Mg(5) + U(5) (Mo added 10, found 9.90); (iv) Au(1) + Pt(0.5) + Ir(0.5) (Mo added 4, found 3.98); (v) Fe(3) + Ni(9), analogous to Hastelloy A (Mo added 2.76, found 2.75) and (vi) Fe(0.25) + Ni (2.5) + Cr(0.75) + W(0.2), analogous to Hastelloy C (Mo added 0.71, found 0.71). The technical samples analysed were : (a) reverberatory flue dust (Mo added 5, 0.01, found 4.97, 0.01); (b) steel BCS 406/1 (Mo 1%, found 0.96%) and (c) BCS 261/1 (Mo 0.11%, found

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0.105%) (average of three determinations). The procedure took 20–35 min for a single to three extractions. As other reducible elements, viz. Ti, U, V, W, Fe, Sb, Bi were separated from molybdenum, its titration for 4–6 mg amounts with Ce^{IV} made series determinations of the element easy.

Experimental

Solutions of molybdenum and other metal ions were prepared as reported earlier⁴. A 20% solution of KSCN (E. Merck) was prepared in deionised water. Ethyl acetate (Qualigens 'SQ') was distilled and the fraction distilling at 76.5–77° was used. Sodium dithionite (Loba, chemic, minimum assay 87%) was used. Wash solution was prepared by mixing 20% KSCN (1 ml) and 5 M HCl (1.6 ml) and diluting to 10 ml with deionised water.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing molybdenum solution with other metal ions in suitable proportions. Reverberatory flue dust samples (0.1 g each) from copper manufacture, containing no Mo, were mixed with known amounts of Mo (50 and 0.1 mg) and fused as reported earlier⁴. The mass was dissolved in water, neutralised with conc. HCl and adjusted to 1 M in HCl in 50 ml volume in each case, and aliquots (5 ml) were taken for analysis. Steel sample (0.1 g) was dissolved as reported earlier⁴. The final volume was made to 50 ml in 1 M HCl and aliquots (5 ml) were taken for analysis.

Procedure : To a sample solution (3–4 ml) containing Mo^{VI} upto 6 mg and other ions were added 20% KSCN (1.5 ml) and 5 M HCl (2 ml). The volume was raised to 10 ml with deionised water and equilibrated with ethyl acetate (10 ml) for 3 min. Two more extractions of ethyl acetate (5 ml each) were made after adding 0.4 ml of 20% KSCN to the aqueous phase, each time. The combined organic phase was shaken with wash solution (10 ml) for 1 min after adding solid sodium dithionite (200 mg). Molybdenum was stripped off the solvent quantitatively by shaking twice, each time for 30 s, with water (10 ml) contain-

ing 20 volume H_2O_2 (2 ml) and made just alkaline with aqueous ammonia. To the combined back-extracts, H_2O_2 (12–15 ml) was added and boiled for 4–5 min, then acidified with HCl and boiled for 3–4 min to decompose H_2O_2 and any polythionate formed⁵. Mo was then determined in milligram amounts either by gravimetric method using oxine⁶ or by titration with Ce^{IV} solution after reduction with hydrazine⁷. For microgram amounts, the organic extract after single extraction was shaken twice with 10 ml each of the wash solution as mentioned above and filtered. The absorbance of the solution was measured at λ_{max} 468 nm and the Mo content obtained. The complex was stable for 1 h, obeyed Beer's law in the range 0–2.6 $\mu\text{g Mo/ml}$ and possessed molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity $1.79 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0057 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

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